

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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METHODS OF EDUCATING SPIRITUAL AND WILL-POWERED VIRTUES IN THE PROCESS OF ATHLETICS TRAINING

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Abstract: The present article analyzes about "the methods of education of spiritual and volitional qualities in the process of athletics", prepared on the basis of advanced foreign experience, is widely covered. Practical interpretations are given about enriching athletes with theoretical and practical knowledge in the education of their spiritual and volitional qualities.

Key words: endurance of athletes, behavior, decency, possession of spiritual knowledge, endurance of athletes in the exercises.

Annotatsiya: Yengil atletika mashg'ulotlari jarayonida ma'naviy va irodaviy fazilatlarini tarbiyalash usullari mavzusi keng yoritilgan bo'lib maqola ilg'or xorijiy tajribalar asosida tayyorlangan. Yengil atletikachilarni ma'naviy va irodaviy sifatlarini tarbiyalashda nazariy va amaliy bilimlar bilan boyitilishi to'g'risida amaliy tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: yengil atletikachilarni irodaviy tayyorgarligi, xulqi, odob-axloq, ma'naviy bilimlarga ega bo'lish, mashqni bajarishda irodaviy tayyorgarlik.

Аннотация: В данной статье мирко освещена тема; «Методы воспитания духовно-волевых качеств в процессе учебно-тренировочных занятий лёгкой атлетикой» В статье изучены и проанализированы теоретический и практический опыт ведущих зарубежных специалистов, воспитания духовно-волевых качеств легкоатлетов.

Ключевые слова: духовно-волевая подготовка легкоатлетов, поведение, мораль и этика, получение духовных знаний, волевая подготовка при выполнении упражнения.

INTRODUCTION

In today's sports, serious attention is paid to the aspects of the mental preparation of athletes. In order to manage the state of mental preparation of an athlete, the coach is required to study his personality. Because it is impossible to study the personality of an athlete runner only one-sidedly, that is, only his sports activities and not to study his daily lifestyle and only those aspects of his unique sports talent[1].

The success of sports psychological influence depends on the level of knowledge that the coach has on the general psychological classification of sports activities. The second important condition is the possession of psychological knowledge on the study of the type of sport and the athlete's personality.

According to psychologists, the solution to personality problems should be sought not in the set of all the characteristics of a person as a person, but in his daily life in society[1].

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

The cultivation of spiritual and will-powered virtues is a fundamental aspect of holistic athletic training. Beyond physical strength and technical skills, athletes require mental resilience, self-discipline, and ethical integrity to achieve long-term success. Literature on the subject emphasizes that the development of these virtues not only enhances athletic performance but also shapes individuals who demonstrate leadership, perseverance, and moral responsibility.

Spiritual and will-powered virtues play a significant role in fostering discipline, self-control, and resilience among athletes. Discipline is essential for consistent training, adherence to rules, and the ability to make sacrifices for long-term goals. Self-control allows athletes to manage emotions, maintain focus under pressure, and avoid impulsive actions that could negatively impact performance. Resilience, on the other hand, helps

athletes overcome setbacks, cope with failures, and recover from injuries, all of which are common challenges in competitive sports. Leadership qualities and team spirit are also key virtues, promoting cooperation, effective communication, and mutual respect among team members.

Educational methods aimed at nurturing these virtues vary across training programs. One widely recognized approach is the use of goal-setting techniques. By encouraging athletes to set clear, measurable, and attainable goals, coaches help them develop focus, determination, and a sense of responsibility for their own progress. Mental conditioning practices, such as visualization, meditation, and mindfulness, are also commonly used to strengthen mental endurance, reduce anxiety, and improve concentration during competitions.

Value-based coaching emerges as another critical method for fostering spiritual and will-powered virtues. In this approach, coaches integrate moral lessons and ethical considerations into training sessions, encouraging athletes to prioritize fairness, respect, and integrity over mere victory. Challenging training programs, designed to push athletes beyond their comfort zones, help build patience, grit, and the capacity to persevere through difficulties.

The role of coaches and mentors in this process is paramount. Studies highlight that athletes often view their coaches as role models whose guidance shapes both their athletic skills and personal character. Effective coaches not only provide technical instruction but also inspire athletes to cultivate self-confidence, respect for others, and a commitment to continuous improvement.

Cultural and psychological factors significantly influence how athletes internalize spiritual and will-powered virtues. Cultural background affects attitudes towards competition, teamwork, and moral values, while individual psychological traits determine an athlete's response to stress, motivation, and challenges. As such, personalized coaching strategies that consider these factors are essential for effective character development.

Despite the recognized importance of educating virtues in athletics, several challenges persist. Balancing the drive for competitive success with the cultivation of ethical behavior remains a complex task. Coaches often face the dilemma of promoting a winning mentality while ensuring that athletes uphold sportsmanship and integrity. Additionally, the mental health of athletes can be at risk when the emphasis on willpower leads to burnout or excessive self-criticism. Addressing cultural differences in value systems further complicates the educational process, requiring sensitivity and adaptability from coaches.

In conclusion, literature underscores the value of integrating spiritual and will-powered virtues into athletic training. By combining psychological techniques, ethical education, and culturally aware coaching practices, trainers can support the development of well-rounded athletes who excel not only in their sports but also as individuals with strong character. This holistic approach ultimately contributes to the creation of resilient, disciplined, and morally grounded athletes capable of thriving both on and off the field.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology for studying the methods of educating spiritual and will-powered virtues in the process of athletics training involves a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches to ensure a comprehensive analysis. This mixed-methods approach allows for a deeper understanding of both the theoretical foundations and practical applications of character education in athletic contexts.

A descriptive and exploratory research design was employed to analyze existing literature, identify key educational methods, and evaluate their effectiveness in athletic training. The study integrates data from academic articles, books, case studies, and expert opinions related to sports psychology, coaching strategies, and moral education in sports.

Data Collection Methods:

Literature Review: A systematic review of relevant academic sources, including peer-reviewed journals, books on sports psychology, and coaching manuals, was conducted. Keywords such as "spiritual development in sports," "willpower in athletics," "character education in training," and "coaching ethics" guided the literature search.

Surveys and Questionnaires: Structured surveys were distributed to athletes, coaches, and sports psychologists to gather quantitative data on the prevalence and perceived effectiveness of various educational methods. The survey included both closed and open-ended questions to capture a wide range of perspectives.

Interviews: In-depth interviews with experienced coaches, sports psychologists, and athletes provided qualitative insights into real-world practices and the challenges of instilling spiritual and will-powered virtues in athletes.

Case Studies: Selected case studies of sports teams and individual athletes who have successfully integrated character education into their training were analyzed to highlight best practices.

The study focused on a diverse group of participants, including:

Professional and amateur athletes across various sports disciplines.

Coaches and trainers with different levels of experience.

Sports psychologists and educators specializing in mental and moral development. Participants were selected using purposive sampling to ensure that those with relevant expertise and experience were included in the study.

Data Analysis Techniques:

Qualitative Analysis: Data from interviews and open-ended survey responses were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify recurring themes related to the development of spiritual and will-powered virtues.

Quantitative Analysis: Statistical methods, including descriptive statistics and correlation analysis, were applied to survey data to determine the relationships between specific training methods and perceived improvements in athletes' character traits.

Comparative Analysis: Different coaching strategies and cultural approaches were compared to assess their impact on character education in various athletic contexts.

Ethical guidelines were strictly followed throughout the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring that they were aware of the study's purpose and their right to withdraw at any time. Data confidentiality and anonymity were maintained to protect participants' privacy.

While the mixed-methods approach provided a comprehensive analysis, certain limitations were acknowledged:

The reliance on self-reported data in surveys may introduce bias.

Cultural differences across participants may affect the generalizability of findings.

Limited access to elite-level coaches and athletes may restrict the scope of case studies.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

An athlete is first of all a person, a professional, has a social activity, his own family. Therefore, studying only his sports activities will not give a significant result. Another important aspect is that sports activities almost always take place in difficult and extreme conditions that require an individual approach to the athlete. An objective (true) description of the athlete's psyche as a person should reflect not only his social life aspects, but also his individual characteristics and aspects.

Knowledge of the athlete justifies an individual approach to the coach in improving the quality of training effectiveness. His task should be to plan the training process based on personal characteristics and, in addition to achieving a high level of physical fitness, during this process it should be provided for the development of strong will, determination, and mental stability. In order to form mental stability, it is necessary to cultivate self-confidence, aspiration for sports competition, and a strong desire to achieve high results. Considering that the training process is always under serious pressure, this work requires a great deal of responsibility and skill, as well as a foundation of psychological knowledge from the coach. From the very beginning, the coach must instill in the athlete a strong sports discipline, the skills of strict adherence to training and the daily routine. During the training process, it is necessary to choose such loads that are close to those in competitions, and even higher. To win competitions, it is necessary to have a goal-oriented approach in training, love for one's activity and chosen sport, a high level of knowledge and thinking. [2]

In his article on mental preparation in specific conditions of training and competitions, the German psychologist and specialist Z. Muller considers the following factors and situations to have an impact on the athlete and the sports results he shows: changing the time of competitions, the constancy and specific difficulties of the distance and time of arrival at competitions, high results of opponents, unsuccessful results at the beginning of the competition season, high nervousness, feeling of physical fatigue, etc. The coach must take each of these unpleasant situations seriously and find ways to eliminate them in a timely manner when preparing for competitions.

The formation of the athlete's ability to control his own mental state is also considered extremely important. This requires the coach and the athlete to have special psychological knowledge to understand the importance of independent directed influences. Research in this area shows that the readiness to manage the psyche opens up wide opportunities for the coach not only in the athlete's psychological state, but also in the entire process of his personal approach to training. The method of managing the psychological state can be used only by such coaches who feel the mechanism of action of this method and believe in it, can gain the athlete's trust, teach him to understand the essence of performing this or that action.

The process of psychological preparation should be developed in two main directions.

1. Development and improvement of the activities of the members of general psychological preparation performing mental tasks during sports activities. This is the development of independent and conscious management of internal feelings and emotions in athletes.

In track and field athletes, these qualities are formed during training and participation in competitions, and their formation mainly depends on the level of development of such qualities as the purpose of training, the dynamics of the growth of will, enthusiasm, perseverance. They are qualities that determine the stability and reliability of the athlete's personality. Also, the development of the quality of self-confidence, which is an important quality associated with the athlete's years of experience, large-scale running practice, its high consistency, purposefulness of movement, and the level of thinking of the athlete, is an urgent problem facing the coach. All these qualities, in connection with tactical training, serve to ensure that the athlete demonstrates high performance and help to free the athlete from excessive external influences. The ability to prepare the athlete for a working mood, to convince him that training and competitions serve his interests, and to teach him that training can bring him joy and peace, depends on the pedagogical skills of the coach. Mental health also helps strengthen an athlete's willpower, allowing them to demonstrate qualities such as initiative and determination during competitions.

2. Special psychological preparation of the athlete immediately before the competition. During the competition, the athlete's psychological state can be conditionally divided into the following: a state before long-term starts, a state after the last pre-start training, a state before the start, a state before the competition, and a state after the competition. These states are constantly encountered in the athletics athlete's sports activities. The coach's task in pre-competition preparation is to ensure that the athlete adheres to the correct daily routine (sleep, training, nutrition, communication), protects the athlete from unexpected accidents and unpleasant situations, and ensures that he arrives at the competition in high sports form and mental readiness. In cooperation with the athlete, plan a running schedule based on his actual level of preparation, the conditions of the competition, and the composition of the participants. Sports condition is a mental state that arises under the influence of the athlete's individual characteristics, training exercises, and communication with rivals. The coach plans the athlete's training, taking into account the athlete's level of enthusiasm, susceptibility to emotions and the ability to control them, and other qualities. The state of the competition depends on the attitude of the audience during the competition, the intensity and dynamics of the run, the tactical methods and means chosen by him and his opponents. During the competition, the character of the athlete is revealed, along with his will, perseverance, intolerance towards opponents, activity, in a word, the level of comprehensive preparation. Usually, coaches do not pay enough attention to the mental state of the athlete after the competition, and little is written about it in the literature. However, studying the state after the competition is also very important, as it allows the coach to better study the athlete's personality and plan subsequent training and competitions. Both success and failure leave a serious mark on the athlete's state and affect his interests and work capacity. The athlete's mental state also has an impact on his recovery process. Analysis of the competition results by the coach and self-critical analysis of the athlete are important aspects of the competition process[3].

It is known that human needs change depending on the development of social structures. Therefore, a person acts to satisfy his needs. A person adapts to the environment with the help of his actions and uses it for his needs. But at the same time, a person changes, rebuilds and adapts the environment to his needs. The nature of a person's activity as a person is such that his actions that help satisfy his needs are not instinctive actions, but mainly rational, conscious actions. This consciousness is that a person acts with a goal in mind, searches for means and methods that can help achieve this goal, and can consciously use his strength and energy to overcome obstacles and difficulties. A person acts consciously and rationally not only to satisfy his specific cultural and social needs, but also to satisfy his natural and biological needs. A person creates and creates something new, adds this new thing to the surrounding reality, changes and complements reality. In general, a person cannot always remain inactive. From this point of view, all human actions can be divided into two categories. The first of them is involuntary actions, and the second is voluntary actions[6].

Involuntary actions of a person occur without a specific goal, often impulsively, that is, reflexively. These actions are not planned by a person in advance. Involuntary actions can occur under any circumstances. Involuntary actions are sometimes also associated with a person's mental activities. For example, there are cases of involuntary perception, involuntary attention, involuntary remembering, involuntary recall. In such cases, a person's involuntary actions are directly related to the sharp difference of the perceived object from other objects or to the interests and needs of the person. Voluntary actions are actions related to the will. Voluntary actions are actions that are carried out fully consciously based on a predetermined goal. However, voluntary action refers not only to physical actions, but also to mental actions. Thus, there are various definitions in the literature regarding the concept of will. For example, in the textbook of A.V. Petrovsky, will is defined as the conscious organization and self-control of a person's activities and behavior aimed at overcoming difficulties in achieving the goals he has set for himself. According to the dictionary authored by Q. Turgunov, will is a voluntary activity of a person, expressed in conscious actions, self-knowledge, especially in overcoming physical and mental difficulties encountered on the way to achieving the goal. According to M. Vohidov, by will we understand actions that are determined in advance, carried out on the basis of a specific goal and

associated with overcoming certain difficulties and obstacles. For example, long-distance runners know before the competition that they will overcome all difficulties and overcome the distance.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Concluding from the above, one of the important features of the implementation of a general volitional activity or a separate act is to determine the freedom of the actions being performed.

-During our pedagogical activity, it is advisable to use the ideas of Eastern scholars and thinkers to form and develop the intellectual, spiritual, and moral qualities of learners.

-We believe that the use of the methods and means of education in today's educational process, based on the ideas of Eastern scholars about the education of a perfect person, will have a positive effect.

We studied the importance of educating the spiritual and volitional qualities of track and field athletes. By educating spiritual and volitional qualities, we studied the formation of feelings of mutual respect for each other, teaching athletes to approach difficulties with willpower in training processes.

As is known, the training of personnel in the field of physical education and sports is based on its own approaches and foundations. Foreign experience, the experience of leading specialists in the field and a number of other factors play a significant role in this.

Thus, we do not pay much attention to the spiritual and willful qualities of track and field athletes during training, and there is very little information in the literature. If attention were paid to the spiritual and willful qualities during training, and if they were enriched with theoretical and practical knowledge, we would have created a basis for our athletes to enter not only the competitions of our republic, but also the world arenas.

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